

Comparing Unfolding Medical Case Studies to Their Individual Single-Item Counterparts

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Case Studies

- Traditional
 - Single extended passage
 - Presents a static medical study from beginning to end
 - All information is present
 - A series of questions are presented alongside

Name _____

Reading Comprehension

A Little Snail

This summer I found a little snail. The snail would slide around by my house. On the days that it would rain, the snail would hide under a rail. Every day when I would go to get the mail, I would visit the snail. One day when I went outside, I did not see the snail. At first I was worried until I looked to my left. The snail was on top of my flower pot. "What a silly snail!" I yelled.

1. What did I find this summer?

2. Where did the snail hide from the rain?

3. Where was the snail at the end of the story?

4. Write three ai words.

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Case Studies

- Traditional
 - Single extended passage
 - Presents a static medical study from beginning to end
 - All information is present
 - A series of questions are presented alongside
- Unfolding
 - Presents medical study incrementally in sequential form
 - Multifaceted information
 - Questions are presented individually as the case unfolds

Unfolding Case Study

Case Study Screen 1 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 17-year-old male client who reports a recent injury to the left thoracic cage.

History and Physical

Client reports injuring his left ribs after being struck by a mechanically pitched baseball in a batting cage last week. He has significant bruising and feels light-headed. He also reports having some intermittent pain in the left shoulder. He denies any shortness of breath, but has some discomfort in the left lower chest when taking a deep breath. He reports feeling abdominal fullness and is occasionally nauseous. Patient has no significant past medical history. His surgical history includes an arthroscopic repair to the left shoulder for a torn rotator cuff last year. He has not felt well enough to attend baseball practice since the injury.

➤ Which of the following assessment findings require **immediate** follow-up? **Select all that apply.**

- productive cough
- BP 90/50, P 116, RR 24
- intermittent left shoulder pain
- ECG showing normal sinus rhythm
- slightly diminished breath sounds on the left
- T 97.8° F (36.6° C), O₂ saturation 98% on room air
- Hgb 9 g/dL (19.0 x 10⁹/L), HCT 27% (0.27), WBC 19,000/mm³ (19.0 x 10⁹/L)
- tenderness upon palpation and dullness to percussion over the abdomen

Unfolding Case Study

Case Study Screen 2 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 17-year-old male client who reports a recent injury to the left thoracic cage.

History and
Physical

Nurses'
Notes

Patient appears pale and slightly diaphoretic. Large amount of bruising noted along the left torso and over the left upper quadrant (LUQ) of the abdomen. Patient is guarded and there is tenderness upon palpation and dullness to percussion over the abdomen. Slightly diminished breath sounds on the left, productive cough noted. Electrocardiogram (ECG) shows normal sinus rhythm.

Unfolding Case Study

Case Study Screen 3 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 17-year-old male client who reports a recent injury to the left thoracic cage.

History and
Physical

Nurses'
Notes

Vital Signs

Laboratory
Results

Vital signs:

- BP 90/50
- P 116
- RR 24
- T 97.8° F (36.6° C)
- O₂ saturation 98% on room air

Unfolding Case Study

Case Study Screen 4 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 17-year-old male client who reports a recent injury to the left thoracic cage.

History and
Physical

Nurses'
Notes

Vital Signs

Laboratory
Results

Laboratory Test	Result	Reference Range
Hemoglobin (Hgb)	9 g/dL (19.0 x 10 ⁹ /L)	Male: 13.2–17.3 g/dL (132–173 g/L) Female: 11.7–15.5 g/dL (117–155 g/L)
Hematocrit (HCT)	27% (0.27)	Male: 39%–50% (0.39–0.50) Female: 35%–47% (0.35–0.47)
White blood cell count (WBC)	19,000/mm ³ (19.0 x 10 ⁹ /L)	5,000–10,000/mm ³ (5–10 x 10 ⁹ /L)

Item Dependencies

- Nuisance factor
- Two main approaches for controlling item dependencies
 - Mathematically modeling the dependencies
 - Higher-order models (e.g., Testlet model)
 - Methodologically
 - Standardized content/materials
 - Test design features

Item Dependencies

- Unfolding case studies
 - Potential for a unique type of item dependency
 - Linear dependency
 - Items may get easier as the case study unfolds
 - Mental schema may get activated through unfolding case study
 - Two approaches to investigate the existence of linear/sequential item dependency
 - Mathematically modeling sequential item dependency
 - LLTM, mixed-effects modeling, etc.
 - Empirical experiment

Case Study vs Independent Items

Analyses

- IRT
 - Anchor on person ability obtained from operational exam
 - Compare calibrations between case study items and individualized items
- LLTM
 - Compare first half and second half of case study items
- Mixed random effects hierarchical model
 - Convert polytomous scores into proportions
 - Random effects on person and items
 - Fixed effects on position
- Response times
 - Median

IRT: Mean Item Difficulty

IRT: Infit

IRT: Outfit

Analyses: LLTM & Mixed effects models

- LLTMs on each unfolding case study
 - First vs Second half
 - All effects of position $\sim < 0.1$ logits (*not significant*; wald test)
- Mixed random effects hierarchical models
 - Random: person & items
 - Fixed: position
 - Effect of position = 0.03 (on the scale of proportion correct)
 - *Not significant*; LRT

Response Times

Response Times

Conclusions

- Unfolding case study do not exhibit main differences in item difficulties when compared to their individualized items
- IRT fit statistics are comparable
- *Regression* analyses show no evidence supporting differential item difficulty as a function of case study item position
- Response data show an initial uptick in response times for the first item in unfolding case studies
 - Effect disappears with subsequent items and unfolding case studies have a temporal advantage